

REPUTATION DIGITAL CURRENCY AND NETWORK DYNAMICS COMPONENTS

D4.2

Fig. 01

Project:	PIE News – Poverty, Income, and Employment News (H2020-ICT-2015)
Duration:	1st July 2016 – 30th June 2019 (36 months)
Contract number:	Grant Agreement Number 687922
Partners:	University of Trento, Basic Income Network Italy, Centre for Peace Studies, Stichting STAFF, CREATE-NET, Stichting Dyne.org, Abertay University, Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute
Document Number:	D4.2
Contractual Date:	31/12/2017
Workpackage:	WP4
Distribution / Types:	PU/Other
Version:	Final
Total Number of Pages:	18
File:	PIE_D4.2_FIN
Authors:	Denis Roio, Aspasia Beneti (Dyne.org)

Design document of digital reputation algorithms and solutions, digital currency and network dynamics monitoring components and software components.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Fig. 02

This document outlines a technical delivery for the Commonfare project consisting in the design and ongoing implementation of an API that facilitates both database driven and blockchain driven value transactions. The vision behind this work is that of providing a flexible software framework for the lean development (Ebert, Abrahamsson, & Oza, 2012) of digital currency and network dynamics, allowing their administration and self-monitoring by the community operating them.

This software project has taken the name of “Social Wallet API” (SWA) and constitutes the building block for integration of external systems, as for instance the “Commonfare” CMS developed by our delivery partner Foundation Bruno Kessler, and the development of standalone systems, as for instance the “Freecoin” wallet adopted in the MACAO Italian pilot.

The scope of this development is that of providing a well proven, test covered (Zhu, Hall, & May, 1997) software component taking care of the most complex tasks related to the interaction with a blockchain and an additional layer of private metadata that is stored on a database. The SWA does that by interfacing itself with the low-level remote process communication layer (RPC) of the Faircoin2 blockchain, while potentially supporting multiple blockchain backends and immediately all those derived from Bitcoin core (Antonopoulos, 2014). Being an API, the SWA provides a self-documenting graphical interface meant for developers; but doesn't provides an end-user graphical interface, since the layer of human-machine interaction is out of the scope of this development. This is because the SWA aims to facilitate the rapid prototyping

(Tripp & Bichelmeyer, 1990) of any interactive pattern using high-level languages that facilitate the agency of interaction designers (Hix & Hartson, 1993).

The main reason to implement the SWA is that of providing layers of autonomy and privacy when operating blockchain backed value transactions in a particular social context. As we have evinced from the pilot studies conducted, it is desirable to have complete transparency on transactions within the context of a particular group or organisation, as well to facilitate their self-monitoring. It is also desirable to protect the use value of the units transacted from crypto market fluctuations: they are provoked by exchange value dynamics that transcend the social use of the blockchain and taint it with the financialisation of its values (Lucarelli, 2010).

The objective of the SWA development then is that of giving multiple layers of techno-political control to the participants. This objective is realised by creating a sort of internal clearing-house mechanism, still leaving open the possibility to have a community managed withdrawal, deposit and basic income (Lucarelli & Fumagalli, 2008) for participants under various conditions that can be debated, customised, modified and scripted according to societal issues rather than technical constraints.

This document is not speculative, but is companion to an actual implementation being developed during the course of the Commonfare project, see <https://github.com/commonfare-net> for a full list of modules, individual links to software modules will be given at the beginning of each section of this document.

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

DATE	VERSION	AUTHOR	SUMMARY OF CHANGES
05/10/2017	V1.0alpha	Denis Roio, Aspasia Beneti	Alpha implementation
02/11/2017	V1.0beta	Denis Roio, Aspasia Beneti	Beta implementation
15/11/2017	V1.0rc1	Denis Roio, Aspasia Beneti	First draft documentation
29/11/2017	V1.0rc2	Denis Roio, Aspasia Beneti	Final draft for revision
06/12/2017	V1.0rc3	Denis Roio, Aspasia Beneti	Completed internal revision
18/12/2017	V1.0	Denis Roio, Aspasia Beneti	Completed consortium revision
22/12/17	FIN	Chiara Bassetti, Daniela Paes Leão	Final version with full VIGs adoption

CONTRIBUTORS

FIRST NAME	LAST NAME	ORGANIZATION	CONTRIBUTION
Denis	Roio	DYNE	Author
Aspasia	Beneti	DYNE	Author
Marco	Sachy	DYNE	Internal review
Pietro Benedetto	Molini	FBK	Internal review
Chiara	Bassetti	UNITN	Final check
Daniela	Paes Leão	MDC	Final visual formatting

ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
AGPLv3	Affero GNU General Public License version 3
DB	Database
DYNE	Stichting Dyne.org (the Netherlands)
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler (Italy)
FXC	Secret Sharing protocol in Freecoin
GPLv3	GNU General Public License version 3
MDC	Museu da Crise (the Netherlands) - including Daniela Paes Leão and Merel Willemsen
REPL	Read-eval-print-loop LISP console
RPC	Remote Process Communication
UNITN	University of Trento (Italy)
SWA	Social Wallet API

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY	3
CONTRIBUTORS	4
ACRONYMS	5
TABLE OF CONTENTS	6
LIST OF FIGURES	8
LIST OF TABLES.....	9
1. LEAN DESIGN STAGE	10
2. OVERVIEW OF COMPONENTS	11
3. SOCIAL WALLET API	12
3.1 REMOTE PROCESS COMMUNICATION.....	12
3.2 LOCAL DOCUMENT DATABASE	12
3.2.1 Transactions.....	13
3.2.2 Tags.....	13
4. JUST-AUTH	14
5. FREECOIN-LIB	15
6. CLJ-STORAGE	16
7. FXC	17
8. FUTURE PLANS	18
REFERENCES	19

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE	TITLE	PAGE
01	Stock image	1
02	Stock image	2
03	Commonopoly - Game developed by Museu da Crise for workshops about digital currency	8
04	SWAGGER site	9
05	Social-Wallet API	10
06	AUTH demo	12
07	Freecoin logo	13
08	Github logo	14
09	Simple Secret Sharing ladies	15
10	Stock image	26

Before delving into the technical and functional description of the SWA, it is necessary to briefly elicit at the outset of this document what the early Commonfare pilots have contributed in terms of design decisions, mostly leaning for database solutions and with only a marginal involvement in crypto blockchains and distributed ledgers. During the research on social currency in D3.1 and D3.2, both the database and crypto blockchain options have been discussed for the three pilots and tested in the MACAO pilot in order to give the richest decision making background context to our research consortium and to the pilot partners involved in the selection of the digital currency assemblage for the Commonfare platform.

For reasons of usability, complexity, transaction and opportunity costs, Macao and the rest of the pilots in Croatia and the Netherlands are opting for a version of

their own coin (in case of MACAO is called “Commoicoin”) whose functionalities include the use of a database, as described in the sections following this one. This is not to say that experimentation with blockchain based currencies, in particular Faircoin2, has been abandoned: MACAO is slowly progressing towards a limited amount of integration justified by real needs. As the Croatian pilot community and project partner Centre for Peace Studies highlighted, a version of Commoicoin with the possibility to convert it in crypto currency is desirable and will be tested with pilot participants in the context of future project activities. A more detailed description of this design has been redacted in Commonfare documents describing the societal research being done and in particular in the deliverables D3.1 (sections 2.3.2, 2.3.3 and 2.3.4) and D3.2 (sections 2.2.2 and 4.1.1).

THE WORLD'S MOST POPULAR API TOOLING

Swagger is the world's largest framework of API developer tools for the OpenAPI Specification(OAS), enabling development across the entire API lifecycle, from design and documentation, to test and deployment.

2. OVERVIEW OF COMPONENTS

DESIGN BUILD DOCUMENT Fig. 04

During the development of the SWA we have made modules out of the monolithic code that was adopted at a early stage of the project in the Italian pilot “MACAO.”² This has improved the clarity of our code and its test coverage (Malaiya, Li, Bieman, & Karcich, 2002), while providing direct access to blockchain operations for other developers in the consortium. At last, this approach serves the open source community at large since other software can also use our libraries and also more advanced pilots can use only what they need as building blocks. For example in the case of the Commonfare.net CMS, it already has authentication functionalities and only needs blockchain functionalities.

All modules are written in Clojure (Hickey, 2008), a dialect of LISP language (McCarthy & Levin, 1965) inheriting its characteristics as a data-centric and non-imperative language working with immutable and persistent data structures, characteristics that greatly improve the reliability of results (Kulkarni, Kailash, Shankar, Nagarajan, & Goutham, 2008). All SWA modules are covered by test units that are verified at every new code change via a

continuous integration pipeline (Duvall, Matyas, & Glover, 2007). The Social Wallet software components are licensed using a free and open source license (GPLv3 and AGPLv3 where applicable), run on open source licensed Java Virtual Machine (OpenJVM 1.7 and 1.8) and are fully cross-platform: one can run them locally on a GNU/Linux machine, as well on Apple/OSX and MS/Windows. Packaging for enterprise JVM infrastructure is provided too.

When designing and implementing the SWA and in general for the whole Freecoin toolkit ecosystem (Roio, Sachy, Lucarelli, Lietaer, & Bria, 2015) we adopted a data-centric approach by adopting declarative data shape descriptions and validations schema (Ceri, Fraternali, & Matera, 2002) on every input and output. The schemas are quoted in the following sections of this document as they are self-descriptive and reflect the shape and requirements of data entities carried on the blockchains and the database.

What follows is a an overview of the modular software components that have been developed.

¹<https://github.com/commonfare-net/freecoin>

Social-wallet-api

Social Wallet REST API backend for webapps. All blockchain activity is backed by a DB. For example for any transaction or move that happens on the blockchain side a record will be created on the DB side and the fees will be updated where applicable.

See more at <https://github.com/pienews/social-wallet-api>

INFO Show/Hide List Operations Expand Operations

LABEL Show/Hide List Operations Expand Operations

POST /wallet/v1/label Show the blockchain label

Implementation Notes
Takes a JSON structure made of a blockchain identifier.

3. SOCIAL WALLET API

Response Content Type

Parameters

Parameter	Value	Description	Parameter Type	Data Type

Fig. 05

URL: <https://github.com/commonfare-net/social-wallet-api>
 Demo: <http://commoncoin.dyne.org:3000/>

This software is made to facilitate the integration of blockchain functions into existing front-end applications, providing an easy backend of documented REST API endpoints that are validated and, in case of error, report meaningful messages.

The Social Wallet API interfaces both with:

- ▶ RPC: the remote protocol communication interface of popular blockchain implementations;
- ▶ DB: the local document database to store transactions and participants private data.

The interaction with the two backends is synchronised and there lies one of the most complex logics that SWA implements. The complexity is hidden by the API to improve the developer experience and will keep improving in the future as its informed by further interaction with pilots and privacy by design practices. What follows is a more detailed explanation of the RPC and DB design choices made, whose implementations are abstracted by Clojure protocols (interfaces) to facilitate code consistency and comprehension according to guidelines established by the research done in the D-CENT project and detailed in its deliverable “Implementation of digital social currency infrastructure” (Roio & Sacy, 2015).

3.1 REMOTE PROCESS COMMUNICATION

The RPC backend interacts with a blockchain storage and, for its own nature, it requires asynchronous verification of confirmations by other blockchain peers. The frequency of such confirmations is not constant and it may vary depending from the consensus algorithm (Vukolić, 2015) of the blockchain implementation as well from the size and load of it in a particular moment in time.

This issue is inherent to all blockchain implementations and often addressed as a priority by projects that aim at adopting blockchain backends for payment and point of sale systems. While such needs are not evident from the pilot research being done in Commonfare, where speed of blockchain transactions comes as relatively unimportant, it is still necessary to have a verification of confirmations on withdrawal and deposit operations in order to consider them valid blockchain operations.

The solution adopted in SWA consists in spawning of a clojure future (VanderHart & Sierra, 2010) to check on a separate thread:

- ▶ if the quantity of blockchain confirmations matches the configured minimum to consider a blockchain transaction as valid;
- ▶ the amount of fees paid for the blockchain transaction to be recognised by peers.

The checks are made via RPC and their progress is saved on the DB. This solution is scalable and coincidentally solves all issues connected to speed of transaction: it offloads the risk for unconfirmed transactions on the clearing-house, for which they become temporary liabilities that are extinguished after a configurable number of confirmations. We consider this a well scalable approach while the temporary liabilities should hardly constitute a concern for social wallets adopted by pilots, since it is clear that the interaction with blockchain backends is discrete and regulated to avoid market-driven value fluctuations.

3.2 LOCAL DOCUMENT DATABASE

The DB backend is implemented using data collections of variable complexity that are matched 1:1 to the data structures used in the sourcecode. The implementation is not bound to a specific database, but provides an abstraction that is adaptable to different database backends. The DB backend also allows to have transactions that are internal to the same wallet and therefore have to pay no fees for “internal” transactions that are made among same-wallet participants.

All operations on data collections are made using aggregate calls that are native to the blockchains and to the database. Data collections are of two types: transactions and tags.

3.2.1 Transactions

Transactions can be both on the blockchain (RPC) and/or on the database (DB). Applications using this first low-level API implementation can choose freely what to do here, according to the business logic being implemented. Transactions made between participants of the same SWA have no need to be registered on the blockchain, but can be just DB based, while an RPC call can check that the clearing-house is actually holding the total capital of funds transacted within the SWA. If a transaction is made across different SWAs or even different sorts of private blockchain wallets, then the transaction is best registered both on the blockchain via RPC and on the local DB. At this stage of development there are still too many undefined aspects that must be observed on pilots in order to elaborate a high-level API that hides this sort of choice, so our choice so far was to make it obvious and expose such functions. Later on we may decide to implement very simple abstractions that group these operations and hide this complexity to application developers using the SWA.

RPC Transaction schema:

```
(s/defschema BTCTransaction
  {(s/required-key "amount") s/Num
   (s/optional-key "category") s/Str
   (s/optional-key "trusted") s/Bool
   (s/optional-key "label") s/Str
   (s/optional-key "vout") s/Num
   (s/optional-key "fee") s/Num
   (s/optional-key "confirmations") s/Num
   (s/optional-key "blockhash") s/Str
   (s/optional-key "blockindex") s/Num
   (s/optional-key "blocktime") s/Num
   (s/optional-key "walletconflicts") [s/Any]
   (s/optional-key "time") s/Num
   (s/optional-key "otheraccount") s/Str
   (s/optional-key "timereceived") s/Num
   (s/optional-key "bip125-replaceable") s/Str
   (s/optional-key "abandoned") s/Bool
   (s/optional-key "comment") s/Str
   (s/optional-key "hex") s/Str
   (s/optional-key "txid") s/Str
   (s/optional-key "address") s/Str
   (s/optional-key "account") s/Str
  })
```

DB Transaction schema:

```
(s/defschema DBTransaction
  "Transaction schema validator"
  {(s/optional-key :tags) [s/Str]
   (s/optional-key :timestamp) s/Str
   (s/optional-key :from-id) s/Any
   (s/optional-key :to-id) s/Any
   (s/optional-key :amount) s/Num
   (s/optional-key :transaction-id) (s/maybe s/Str)
   (s/optional-key :currency) s/Str
   ;; how many confirmations needed for a transaction to be confirmed
   (s/optional-key :number-confirmations) s/Num
   ;; and how often should that be checked
   (s/optional-key :frequency-confirmations) s/Num}}
```

The schemas are still subject to slight changes and should not be considered final at this stage of the project, but at a later stage, as they also depend to Faircoin2 API changes.

3.2.2 Tags

Tags have been implemented as a familiar interface for creating and retrieving particular search keys: they are a popular system adopted by most social platforms for the collaborative creation of communal hierarchical taxonomies (Heymann & Garcia-Molina, 2006). It is extremely intuitive for users to add multiple tags to any transaction and retrieve lists or even graphical statistics about them in a later self-monitoring stage, allowing every participant to run an audit or draw a balance based on tags. But while interacting with tags is intuitive, implementing them is rather complex and often too demanding for interface designers. For this reason we decided to implement tags in the back-end of the Freecoin toolkit, exposing this intuitive searching system to the SWA and therefore to any front-end application developing on it.

Tag transaction schema:

```
(s/defschema Tag
  "Tag schema validator"
  ;; tag(string) created-by(string) created(timestamp)
  {(s/required-key :tag) s/Str
   (s/required-key :count) s/Num
   (s/required-key :amount) s/Num
   (s/required-key :created-by) s/Any
   (s/required-key :created) s/Any}}
```


4. JUST-AUTH

Fig. 06

URL: <https://github.com/commonfare-net/just-auth>

This module is a simple, readable and test covered implementation of an authentication system that supports two-factor authentication via email and eventually other systems that may be required by pilots.

The system stores secrets conforming to RFC2898 and uses the PBKDF2 abstract password-based derivation function (Josefsson, 2011) with a SHA512 hashing algorithm, thus compliant with ISO/IEC 11770-6:2016. Further compliance with key management directives for financial services (ISO 11568-2:2012) will be pursued as the development progresses.

The authentication schema for a single account:

```
(s/defschema AccountDetails
  {(s/required-key "account")          s/Str
   (s/required-key "address")         s/Str
   (s/required-key "category")       s/Str
   (s/required-key "amount")         s/Num
   (s/required-key "label")          s/Str
   (s/required-key "vout")           s/Num
   (s/optional-key "fee")            s/Num
   (s/optional-key "abandoned")     s/Bool})
```


5. FREECOIN-LIB

Fig. 07

URL: <https://github.com/commonfare-net/freecoin-lib>

The Freecoin-lib is the library implementing RPC communication with multiple blockchain backends, it provides basic 1:1 functionalities as well more high-level functionalities. It has been designed after Bitcoin's RPC API which is compatible with a number of derivatives and in particular the Faircoin2 implementation that the Commonfare consortium evaluates to adopt.

Blockchain implementations can be added easily following a protocol abstraction (like an interface) that defines the main functions that should be exposed to any software application including the library.

Blockchain protocol abstraction:

```
(defprotocol Blockchain
  ;; blockchain identifier
  (label [bk])

  ;; account
  (import-account [bk account-id secret])
  (create-account [bk name])
  (list-accounts [bk])

  (get-address [bk account-id])
  (get-balance [bk account-id])
  (get-total-balance [bk])
```

```
;; transactions
(list-transactions [bk params])
(get-transaction [bk txid])
(create-transaction [bk from-account-id amount to-account-id params])
(update-transaction [bk txid fn])
(move [bk from-account-id amount to-account-id params])

;; tags
(list-tags [bk params])
(get-tag [bk name params])
(create-tag [bk name params])
(remove-tag [bk name])

;; vouchers
(create-voucher [bk account-id amount expiration secret])
(redeem-voucher [bk account-id voucher])
(list-vouchers [bk])
```

This abstraction is subject to further changes until the end of the project.

6. CLJ-STORAGE

Fig. 08

URL: <https://github.com/commonfare-net/clj-storage>

This software module is a rather simple abstraction for NOSQL document storage. It currently supports MongoDB and can be extended to support more back-ends as needed. It is a simple connector and its base functionalities are as well covered with tests.

Rather than directly using a database implementation, this abstraction was planned to enable the possibility of implementing multiple DB backends capable of modeling the data in different ways and apply algorithms beyond the mere aggregation calls provided by MongoDB.

This approach is validated by the fact that, just two months before the time of writing this deliverable, the analysis made

in D3.2 concludes in section 4.2 that the K-core algorithm (Batagelj & Zaversnik, 2003) applied on a graph database is the best suitable approach for “recognizing and measure contributions to the Commonfare”.

Such a theoretical research findings would imply a huge effort in terms of implementation, considering the linear topology of storage on blockchains and the hierarchical organisation of information in NOSQL document databases; but the implementation of this abstraction will make this new requirement feasible within the span of the Commonfare project.

7. FXC

Fig. 09

URL: <https://github.com/dyne/fxc>
 DEMO: <http://secrets.dyne.org/>

The “FXC” cryptographic protocol is used to split a secret string in multiple parts and to recover it using some of these parts (quorum). The FXC protocol and its use case (mostly related to social digital currency) are explained in the “Implementation of digital social currency infrastructure” produced as part of the research conducted in the D-CENT project (FP7 grant number 610349).

In the course of Commonfare early development FXC has been adapted to function as a web based “secret sharing” application to demonstrate its capabilities and also pilot its use in some isolated cases related to socially shared

password storage and contract signing.

FXC addresses the following standards:

Information technology – Security techniques – Secret sharing - [ISO/IEC 19592-1:2016](#) (Part 1: General) - [ISO/IEC FDIS 19592-2](#) (Under development) (Part 2: Fundamental mechanisms)

The Secret Sharing algorithm (Knuth, 1997) adopted is best known as Shamir’s Secret Sharing (Shamir, 1979), using the popular Java implementation by Tim Tiemens with a 4096 bit long prime number. The Integer Compression algorithm used internally is FastPFOR128 (Lemire & Boytsov, 2015).

8. FUTURE PLANS

Fig. 10

The development of SWA in Commonfare had so far a very limited interaction with pilot dynamics, mostly limited to the good relationship and dynamic exchange with the MACAO pilot in Italy that has adopted and informed the development of most features. We expect this to change in the next phases of the project to inform and refine further design and implementation choices. We think this is very feasible especially considering the growing understanding of the role for SWA in the community dynamics and considering the Commonfare consortium is orienting itself to facilitate the creation of internal value exchange circuits (DB based) that may or may not interface themselves with different blockchains via RPC.

Another important part that will be further developed is the integration and usability of the FXC protocol in order to facilitate clearing-house administrators in their tasks while avoiding the centralised liability of a single participant. Actions taken on behalf of the clearing-house

will be separated from those of a single participant wallet and subject to approval conditioned by cryptography proof based on the FXC secret sharing implementation. Such proofs will also require two-factor authentication schemes implemented in the Just-auth module.

At last we are proceeding to the creation of an administration console for advanced usage of the SWA and scripting of its functions: this module is based on a web based read-eval-print-loop interface (REPL) and inspired by pedagogic programming environments (Findler, Flanagan, Flatt, Krishnamurthi, & Felleisen, 1997) to facilitate live coding (Collins, McLean, Rohrer, & Ward, 2003) and fast prototyping of simple scripts as for instance defining timed basic income distribution or contractual conditions by which transactions should be activated or tags applied. A first prototype is visible at the URL <https://github.com/commonfare-net/social-wallet-admin-console> and already offers some functionality.

REFERENCES

- Antonopoulos, A. M. (2014). *Mastering bitcoin: Unlocking digital cryptocurrencies*. “ O’Reilly Media, Inc.”
- Batagelj, V. and Zaversnik, M., (2003). An O (m) algorithm for cores decomposition of networks. In *arXiv preprint cs/0310049*.
- Ceri, S., Fraternali, P., & Matera, M. (2002). Conceptual modeling of data-intensive web applications. *IEEE Internet Computing*, 6(4), 20–30. IEEE.
- Collins, N., McLean, A., Rohrhuber, J., & Ward, A. (2003). Live coding in laptop performance. *Organised sound*, 8(3), 321–330. Cambridge University Press.
- Duvall, P. M., Matyas, S., & Glover, A. (2007). *Continuous integration: Improving software quality and reducing risk*. Pearson Education.
- Ebert, C., Abrahamsson, P., & Oza, N. (2012). Lean software development. *IEEE Software*, 29(5), 22–25. Citeseer.
- Findler, R. B., Flanagan, C., Flatt, M., Krishnamurthi, S., & Felleisen, M. (1997). DrScheme: A pedagogic programming environment for scheme. In *International symposium on programming language implementation and logic programming* (pp. 369–388). Springer.
- Heymann, P., & Garcia-Molina, H. (2006). *Collaborative creation of communal hierarchical taxonomies in social tagging systems*. Stanford.
- Hickey, R. (2008). The clojure programming language. In *Proceedings of the 2008 symposium on dynamic languages* (p. 1). ACM.
- Hix, D., & Hartson, H. R. (1993). *Developing user interfaces: Ensuring usability through product & process*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Josefsson, S. (2011). PKCS# 5: Password-based key derivation function 2 (pbkdf2) test vectors.
- Knuth, D. E. (1997). *The art of computer programming, volume 2: Seminumerical algorithms*. Addison-Wesley Longman Publishing Co., Inc., Boston, MA.
- Kulkarni, P., Kailash, H., Shankar, V., Nagarajan, S., & Goutham, D. (2008). *Programming languages: A comparative study*. Information Security Research Lab, NITK, Surathkal.
- Lemire, D., & Boytsov, L. (2015). Decoding billions of integers per second through vectorization. *Software: Practice and Experience*, 45(1), 1–29. Wiley Online Library.
- Lucarelli, S. (2010). *Financialization as biopower*. MIT Press.
- Lucarelli, S., & Fumagalli, A. (2008). Basic income and productivity in cognitive capitalism. *Review of social economy*, 66(1), 71–92. Taylor & Francis.
- Malaiya, Y. K., Li, M. N., Bieman, J. M., & Karcich, R. (2002). Software reliability growth with test coverage. *IEEE Transactions on Reliability*, 51(4), 420–426. IEEE.
- McCarthy, J., & Levin, M. I. (1965). *LISP 1.5 programmer’s manual*. MIT press.
- Roio, D., & Sacy, M. (2015). Implementation of digital social currency infrastructure. EU-FP7/D-CENT proj.nr. 610349.

Roio, D., Sachy, M., Lucarelli, S., Lietaer, B., & Bria, F. (2015). Design of social digital currency. EU-FP7/D-CENT proj.nr 610349.

Shamir, A. (1979). How to share a secret. *Communications of the ACM*, 22(11), 612–613. ACm.

Tripp, S. D., & Bichelmeyer, B. (1990). Rapid prototyping: An alternative instructional design strategy. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 38(1), 31–44. Springer.

VanderHart, L., & Sierra, S. (2010). Parallel programming. *Practical Clojure*, 159–166. Springer.

Vukolić, M. (2015). The quest for scalable blockchain fabric: Proof-of-work vs. bft replication. In *International workshop on open problems in network security* (pp. 112–125). Springer.

Zhu, H., Hall, P. A., & May, J. H. (1997). Software unit test coverage and adequacy. *Acm computing surveys (csur)*, 29(4), 366–427. ACM.